

MANAGEMENT OF MINOR AILMENTS OF PREGNANCY WITH AYURVEDA

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ABSTRACT

Present review article is related to pregnancy. Mother is the biggest blessing of God to Mankind. Only a physically, mentally & socially healthy mother can give birth to a healthy child. Although pregnancy is a natural phenomenon but woman may encounter some of the ailments like nausea, vomiting, constipation, acidity etc. which may be perceived by her as major ones. But these are the minor ailments of pregnancy which need simple explanation, counseling & sometimes treatment. Counseling is necessary to reassure the patient & make her comfortable. Most educated & informed patients are worried about the safety of medications prescribed during pregnancy. Ayurveda provides a safe & side-effect free treatment through dietary regulation, Ayurveda remedies, and personalized lifestyle modifications, and ensures the well-being of both mother and fetus.

INTRODUCTION

The power of regeneration is the greatest gift endowed by God upon Mankind. As an instrument of nature, in the multiplication of the human race, woman has a pivot role to play. The minor ailments like nausea, vomiting etc. which a woman generally faces during pregnancy can be effectively treated by Ayurveda. There is no difference in the physical or physiological disorders of a pregnant woman from any other individual, because doshas & dushyas of the body are same. Principles of treatment differ, because use of any punjent etc. drug during pregnancy is likely to

harm the fetus. Considering this very fact the Acharyas have advocated principles of treatment for a pregnant woman and have also given description of a few disorders afflicting the woman exclusively during pregnancy.

Realising the importance of the subject Acharya Kashyapa has given two full chapters on this and has emphasized that proper management of disorders during pregnancy is helpful for protection & development of both mother & fetus.

Acharya Harita has enlisted Sosa (emaciation), hrillasa (nausea), chardi (vomiting), shofa (oedema), jwara (fever), aruchi (anorexia), atisara (diarrhea) & vivarnata (discoloration) etc. eight disorders which afflict the pregnant woman. These disorders include both minor & major ailments of pregnancy, but here only minor ailments of pregnancy will be considered.

- Anemia
- Nausea & Vomiting
- Backache
- Breast discomfort
- Constipation
- Fatigue
- Excessive sweating, feeling of warmth & palpitation.
- Leg cramps
- Vaginal discharge
- Groin pain
- Acidity & heart burn
- Varicose vein
- Ankle edema
- Effects on the urinary tract.

General Principles of Treatment of Pregnant women according to Ayurveda-

- Treat Pregnant woman with the use of soft, sweet, cold, pleasant & gentle drugs, dietetics & behavior.
- Do not give emetics & purgatives to pregnant woman.
- If the disease is acute or serious, emetics should be given followed by use of sweet & sour edibles mixed with anulomaka (carminative) drugs.
- Use of vatsaka, pipalli, sunthi and fruit of amalaki can be advised.
- Unripe fruit of Bilva mixed with curd & sugar is always beneficial.

Ayurvedic treatment includes both Aahar & Vihar Chikitsa. Thus, these minor ailments of pregnancy are managed by both or any one of the above type of treatment. Many of the minor ailments of pregnancy are perceived as complications and therefore become matter of concern to the patient. They need simple medical explanation, counseling, change in life style, diet & attitudes.

AIM

To explore and present a comprehensive review of Ayurvedic principles and treatment modalities for the management of minor ailments in pregnancy, integrating classical knowledge with contemporary clinical evidence to support safe, effective, and holistic maternal care.

OBJECTIVES

1. To identify and describe the most common minor ailments experienced during pregnancy, including nausea, vomiting, constipation, backache, fatigue, heartburn, edema, and others.
2. To document Ayurvedic perspectives on the etiopathogenesis (Nidana and *Samprapti*) of these minor ailments based on classical Ayurveda texts.
3. To review Ayurvedic treatment approaches including *Aahara* (diet), *Vihara* (lifestyle), and *Oushadha* (medications) that are recommended for managing these ailments in a safe and pregnancy-compatible manner.
4. To correlate classical Ayurvedic practices with current biomedical and clinical research, examining evidence-based studies on herbs and practices commonly used in Ayurveda for antenatal care.
5. To emphasize the importance of counselling and non-pharmacological management (*Adravyabhoot chikitsa*) in improving maternal comfort and reducing anxiety associated with minor pregnancy disorders.
6. To propose an integrative, evidence-backed approach that can be adopted by clinicians for better antenatal care without compromising fetal safety.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This narrative review was conducted with the aim to explore Ayurvedic approaches to managing minor ailments during pregnancy and to integrate classical principles with modern scientific insights. This search used keywords Ayurveda and pregnancy and nausea/constipation/backache in PubMed, Scopus, Cochrane Library and Google Scholar. Randomised controlled trials (RCTs), systematic reviews and pertinent observational studies were prioritised. Core classical references were screened to map traditional aetiology and therapeutics.

DISCUSSION

Details discussion of minor ailments in pregnancy as below-

ANAEMIA

First of all before discuss all the other minor ailments, Anaemia in pregnancy & its Ayurvedic treatment is described. Anaemia is the most common haematological disorder occurring in pregnancy. Anaemia can be considered both minor as well as major ailment of pregnancy. When we consider it as occurring due to physiological deficiency of iron during pregnancy then it is a minor ailment, which can be simply treated by maintaining balanced diet which may be supplemented with oral iron. But if it is pathological i.e. occurring due to severe hemorrhage, bleeding disorders, thalassemia, other haemoglobinopathies, bone marrow insufficiency, infection like malaria or tuberculosis, chronic disease etc. then it is a major one & it needs detailed investigation & proper treatment.

Hb level below 10 gm/dl at any time during pregnancy is considered anaemia. It is of various types, but in obstetrics, deficiency anaemia & haemorrhagic anaemia are more concerned. Deficiency anaemia can be effectively treated by Ayurvedic management.

During pregnancy there always remains physiological iron deficiency due to disproportionate increase in plasma volume, RBC volume, Hb mass & extra iron demand especially in the second half of pregnancy. If the Hb% during second half of pregnancy is 10 gm%, RBC-3.2 million/mm³, PCV-30%, peripheral smear shows normal morphology of the RBC with central pallor, it should be maintained by taking proper balanced diet rich in iron, proteins & vitamins & which is easily digestible. Food should preferably be cooked in iron utensils.

Recommended daily intake of iron in pregnant woman is 30 to 60 mg. A list of iron rich foods is given below-

Food	Milligrams of iron per 100 gm food
1)Non-veg	
Chicken/beef liver	8.8
Cooked beef	5.5
Cooked turkey meat	4.8
Tuna fish in oil	1.2
Cooked chicken	0.8
<i>Remember iron from raw food is absorbed better.</i>	

2)Veg	
a)fruits-i)fresh fruits-	
Banana	0.5
Grapes	1.5
Guava	0.27
Mango	1.3
Orange	0.32
Sitaphal	4.31
Amla	1.2
ii)Dry fruits-	
Dates	7.3
Raisins	7.7
Almonds	4.4
Dried figs	4.0
b)vegetables-	
Cooked spinach	3.5
Cooked green peas	1.4
Cooked potato	1.4
turnip greens	2
Beet, mustard, kale	2
c)Rice, Millets, Pulses-	
Raw husked rice	4
Raw under milled rice-	2.2
Raw miled rice	2
Jowar	4.1
Bajra	8
Ragi	3.9
Bengal gram	4.6
Black gram	3.8
Red gram	2.7
Soyabean	10.4
Foods rich in vit.C are known to increase iron absorption.Alist of foods rich in vit.C is given below-	
a)Fruits-	

Amla	600
Guava	212
Lime	63
Orange	30
Tomato	27
b)Vegetables-	
Cabbage	124
Spinach	28
Brinjal	12
Cauliflower	56
Potatoes	17
Radish	15
c)Germinated pulses-	
Bengal gram	16

This diet can be supplemented with Ayurvedic iron preparations from second trimester onwards. Daily oral administration of 500mg of any one of the following, two times daily is quite effective-

- *Punarnava Mandoor*
- *Dhatri Lauha*
- *Saptamrita Lauha*
- *Navayasa Lauha*
- *Tapyadi Lauha*
- *Swarna Makshika Bhasm*

Along with this *Deepan Pachan* drug should also be given so as to improve the appetite and facilitate digestion. Oral iron therapy should be prescribed from the second trimester of pregnancy. This prophylactic treatment reduces the chances of anemia in later part of pregnancy & is also helpful in management of already existing anemia.

NAUSEA & VOMITTING-

Nausea & vomiting are very common ailment of pregnancy. Most of the pregnant woman (70%) experience nausea in the first trimester of pregnancy, usually common in primigravidae. Cause is not clear, but may be due to increase in chorionic gonadotropin or may be psychological. Symptom mostly occurs in early

hours of the morning upon waking up. Certain smells are likely to aggravate the symptom. In some women, it may persist throughout the pregnancy. Emotionally unstable women are more susceptible.

All the Ayurvedic classics have mentioned excessive salivation & nausea etc. as a symptom of normal pregnancy i.e. *Vyaktagarbha Lakshana*. In the description of disease *Chardi*, *Acharya Sushruta* has enlisted pregnancy also as a causative factor under its fifth type i.e. *Agantuja Chardi*, *Dauhrda* is also enumerated in etiology.

Dalhana has explained that non-fulfillment of *Dauhrda* & presence of fetus as cause of vomiting.

In *Madhukosa* Commentary it is mentioned that *Vayu* is being pushed upward by fetus gets provoked and causes vomiting. For its management assessment of relative predominance of various doshas should be made.

Above mentioned etiopathogenesis clarifies three specific causes for vomiting during pregnancy-

a) *Vatavaigunya*- Vata denotes nervous system including psychology of individual. Thus its abnormality may cause vomiting by increased or abnormal reflex action. Thus it can be considered as reflex & psychogenic factors for causing vomiting during pregnancy.

b) *Dauhrda Avamanana* or non-fulfillment of *Dauhrda*-Normally those substances are desired by the woman for whom she is deficient. Their non-fulfillment may produce certain deficiency & this may produce vomiting.

C) *Garbha nimitta* or due to fetus-When there is no other demonstrable cause, then vomiting occurs either due to immune response of woman for trophoblastic hormones or idiopathic.

TREATMENT-

- Ashwasan chikitsa i.e. counselling.
- Advice to prefer solid food over liquid.
- Eat a piece of toast or biscuit on rising or before getting out of bed.
- Take small frequent feeds.
- Have desired fruits.
- Avoid fried, fatty & distasteful food.
- Nausea is relieved by use of pestled bhunimba with honey.

- Vomiting is relieved by use of-
 - (i) Pestled *Bhunimba* with equal quantity of sugar.
 - (ii) Paste of *Dhanyak* mixed with rice water and sugar.
- Cardamom seeds along with honey relieve vomiting.
- Use of mayurpicch bhasm in dosage of 250-500mg along with sitopaladi choorna-3gm two times daily is also very effective in curing both nausea & vomiting.
- Dadimashtaka choorna in dosage of 3-6gm, two times daily increases appetite and relieves nausea.
- Chardiripu vati-250mg – two times daily is also effective.
- Bilvadi lehyam-1tsf two times daily is effective.
- Matulunga rasayana is also effective.
- Beneficial diet-The diet should be sweet with little quantity of fat & salt and light. It should be taken repeatedly in small amounts followed by little quantity of water.
- Allopathic antiemetics drugs like metoclopramide, domperidone, cisapride and ondansetron should be avoided during pregnancy.

Ayurvedic treatment given for vomiting in pregnancy is safe for both mother & fetus and thus it can be used safely.

BREAST DISCOMFORT-

Most women often experience heaviness, tingling & discomfort or tenderness in their breasts during early pregnancy. This occurs due to hormonal changes during pregnancy causing hypertrophy & enlargement of the ductal & alveolar system and increased vascularity of breast. As the pregnancy advances, breast progressively increase in size, there is increase in pigmentation, formation of secondary areola & appearance of Montgomery tubercles. Sometimes a clear secretion may be expressed out at the nipples.

In Ayurvedic classics Acharya Sushruta & Vagbhatta have described the formation of placenta that due to obstruction of orifices of artavavaha srotas by fetus, the artava goes upwards, gets accumulated and forms placenta, left over artava moves further upwards & helps in the development of breast & increases black pigmentation of areola & lips etc.

TREATMENT

As it is a physiological change therefore it needs no treatment. Only counselling is sufficient. Patient should be advised to wear loose clothes.

BACKACHE-

Nearly 50% of pregnant women suffer from backache. Exaggeration of the lumbosacral lordosis due to protrusion of the abdomen caused by the enlarging gravid uterus leads to backache in pregnancy. With advancing pregnancy, there is a steady increase in the load on the abdominal & back muscles causing swaying of the pelvis & flat feet & thus contributing to backache in pregnancy. Heavy work involving bending, lifting heavy weights & twisting of spine cause backache. Backache will be exaggerated in those women who have been suffering from it prior to pregnancy.

Backache may be –

- a) Physiological backache in pregnancy
- b) Pathological

Physiological backache in pregnancy is located in the lumbosacral region; it is diffuse in distribution and not associated with any sensory or motor deficiency.

Pathological causes include-slipped disc, spondylosis, osteoarthritis & osteophytic growths. This gives rise to localized pain. Associated radiating pain to the lower thighs & abdomen may also be present. Point of pain can be localized on palpation.

TREATMENT-

- Avoid bending, lifting heavy weights and strenuous activity.
- Avoid wearing high heeled footwear.
- Muscular spasm, urinary infection & constipation can also cause backache-so treat them if present.
- Massaging the back muscles with vatahara taila like Mahanarayana taila or Panchguna taila or Dashmool taila and taking proper rest may relieve pain due to muscle spasm.
- Diet should contain enough green leafy vegetables, grains, fruits & nuts.
- Correct posture, resting on a hard bed & yoga are also helpful.
- Avoid stress

- All pathological backaches should be referred to an orthopaedic surgeon.

CONSTIPATION-

Many women complain of constipation after onset of pregnancy. This occurs due to rising level of progesterone which affect the motility of the smooth muscle of the gut and reduced levels of 'motilin' leading to reduced peristalsis & a greater degree of stasis. Increased fluid absorption due to pregnancy & the effect of medications like hematinic further increase the problem.

TREATMENT-

- Counseling about bowel movements.
- Pay attention to bowel urge. Do not ignore it.
- Do exercises to tone up body muscles.
- Diet should be in adequate quantity and it should be rich in fiber content, green leafy vegetables & fruits.
- Drink plenty of fluids-at least 10 glasses per day.
- Eat raw fruits except papaya.
- Lemon juice with water before breakfast may be helpful.
- Herbal Ayurvedic medicines act as bulk purgatives and are safe during pregnancy.eg-Isabgol-1tsf at night with lukewarm water.
- Avipattikar choorna-5gm with lukewarm water two times daily after meals, is also beneficial.
- Munakkka-2-4 piece, bedded in lukewarm milk, if taken at night relieves constipation.
- Trifla choorna-6gms with leukwarm water at night relieves constipation.
- Acharya Charaka & Vagbhatta have mentioned the management of vibandh (constipation) occurring due to udavarta during pregnancy. It is treated with vatahara & snigdha annapana along with use of anuvasana basti with oil prepared with madhuka. If it is not cured by this procedure then niruha basti should be given.

FATIGUE-

Tiredness, fatigue & disinclination to attend to daily domestic chores are also common in pregnant woman. This problem is further aggravated by emotional factors, sympathy seeking & coping day to day problems along with disturbed food & disturbed sleep. These features are similar to the features of Sadyograhita Garbha described in Ayurvedic classics- Signs/Symptoms of recently conceived woman are fatigue, languor, thirst, lassitude of thighs etc.

TREATMENT— No specific treatment is required.

- Reassurance
- Advice to take adequate rest.
- Avoid stress
- Take proper diet & sleep.

FEELING OF WARMTH, EXCESSIVE SWEATING & PALPITATION-

These symptoms occurring in pregnancy resemble to the symptoms found in hyperthyroidism. They occur due to HCG & thermogenic effects of progesterone. Thyroid profile should be done to rule out hyperthyroidism.

TREATMENT-

- No treatment is needed.
- Rest in cool & calm place.
- Wear loose fitting cotton clothes.

VAGINAL DISCHARGE-

During pregnancy most women experience vaginal discharge. This is attributed to the increase in vascularity of the vaginal walls during pregnancy. If the discharge is excessive, curdy or yellowish white in nature & accompanied with symptoms like vulval pruritis or dysuria or both then an examination of the discharge for candidal/ trichomonal vaginitis should be done and suitable treatment should be prescribed. In advanced pregnancy copious watery discharge must raise the suspicion of amniotic fluid leak following premature rupture of membranes. Collection of this fluid on the blade of the speculum & its examination will reveal the fluid to be alkaline with presence of fetal squames in it.

TREATMENT-

- Assurance
- Advice for local cleanliness.

- If the discharge is non-purulent, non-offensive, without any pain, burning sensation or discomfort it is physiological leucorrhoea of pregnancy & it needs no treatment.
- Amlaki choorna-3gms mixed with sugar can be taken.
- Combination of lodhra choorna-2gm, Pushyanuga choorna-2gm, Sitopaladi choorna-2gm & Godanti bhasm-250-500 mg two times daily with milk is also very effective.

HEART BURN OF PREGNANCY-

It occurs due to the effect of progesterone on sphincter at gastro-oesophageal junction. The acid contents of the stomach regurgitate into the mouth causing acid discomfort.

TREATMENT-

- Avoid meals at late night.
- Avoid spicy & fried foods.
- Evening walks to facilitate digestion.
- Eat small meals rather than large meals.
- Avoid liquid with meals. They should be taken at least half an hour before or after meals.
- Never lie down after a meal. It is better that you sit.
- Coconut water is beneficial.
- If problem still persists, then following medical treatment should be given-
 1. Satavari Choorna-3gms., two times daily with milk + Varatika bhasm-250 mg + Dhatri Lauha-500mg two times daily with ghee or honey.
 2. Avipattikara Choorna-3gm, two times daily after meals.

ANKLE OEDEMA-

It may be physiological or pathological. No treatment is required for physiological edema. It subsides on rest by keeping legs slightly elevated. Pathological ankle edema needs proper treatment.

PROBLEMS OF URINARY TRACT-

(a)Frequency of micturition- During early pregnancy, pressure is exerted by the enlarging gravid uterus on the base of the bladder causing bladder irritation leading to increased frequency of micturition. When the enlarging uterus grows out of the pelvis to become an abdominal organ, this symptom generally disappears. In late pregnancy, when the fetal head gets engaged then this symptom appears again.

TREATMENT-No treatment is required.

(b)Burning micturition-Due to the effect of progesterone on the smooth muscle of the pelvi -calyceal system there is dilatation and an increase in capacity, poor peristalsis of the uterus leading to stasis of urine. Thus there is increased tendency of urinary tract infections.

TREATMENT-

- Drink plenty of water.
- Drink cold milk mixed with sugar & cardamom.
- Gokshura choorna-3gms + Amrita satva -500mg, two times daily with milk is also very effective.
- Decoction of trina panchmool with gokshur-50ml, two times daily is effective.
- Chandraprabha vati -500mg, two times daily is beneficial.
- Avipattikar choorna(3gms)+ Pittantaka(500mg) is also effective.
- Chandanasava-20ml with equal quantity of water, daily after meals helps in relieving burning micturition.

CONCLUSION

1. Urbanization,
2. Most of the minor ailments need counseling and simple medical explanation.
3. Balanced diet and proper lifestyle, helps to overcome these problems.
4. Self-medication should be avoided. Always consult your obstetrician for appropriate treatment.
5. Never ignore vaginal bleeding, persistent pain, fever or any other constitutional symptoms. These should be promptly reported.
6. Importance of drugs prescribed by obstetrician must be emphasized.
7. Importance of regular Antenatal checkups should be explained.
8. Advice on following should be given-
 - Sleep & rest
 - Care of the breasts
 - Bathing
 - Coitus

- Clothing
- Dental care
- Immunization
- Travel
- Smoking & alcohol

9. Always avoid stress during pregnancy.

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